

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe

Phase 2

Workflow Extensions

Milestone 4.2 - MS9

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Achieved: Yes

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Summary

The milestone target was to report on the delivery of software to deliver tight integration between the scheduler (CYLC) and the I/O middleware (ESDM) so as to support maximally efficient use of storage resources during pre-exascale workflows. However, as the work was being done, analysis showed that the benefits available at this time of carrying out the planned tight integration would not warrant completing all the software development; we believe the existing level of integration with the scheduler running code which includes storage configuration delivers on the underlying requirements. Accordingly, we mark the milestone complete (the underlying requirement has been met), and have redeployed resource yielded by not completing the tight integration software on other aspects of WP4.

Detail

The initial plan for the development and usage of the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) envisaged scenarios where the integration of the scheduler (CYLC) and the ESDM would allow the ESDM to manage data placements in a more efficient manner, thus improving simulation throughput.

The first action for this task was to develop those scenarios in more detail for the actual environments of interest. We then we analyzed the potential CYLC and ESDM interactions and made a rough architectural plan. This work was published in “Potential of I/O Aware Workflows in Climate and Weather” (Kunkel and Pedro, 2020). The key contributions of that paper were to deliver:

1. A sketch of a vision for an integrated data-driven approach, with a discussion of the associated challenges and implications, and
2. An architecture and roadmap consistent with this vision that would allow a seamless integration into current climate and weather workflows as it utilises versions of existing tools (ESDM, Cylc, XIOS, and DDN’s IME).

The primary expected benefit of this vision is that workflows could be made more efficient on systems that provide multiple storage systems such as either node-local and cluster-wide storage or that host multiple cluster-wide storage systems. For DKRZ, for instance, the performance of 3,000 node-local SSDs (~100 MiB/s each, 300 GiB/s aggregated) can augment the performance of two available Lustre file systems nicely (~200+500 GiB/s).

Next, we investigated the model workflows which would be needed to deliver on ESIWACE specific goals (where we could then test any developments). Our work had identified three criteria for delivering the proposed tight integration: the problem

needed to be large; there needed to be multiple-steps (so the scheduler integration is important); and the workflow needs to be run on systems with multiple tiers of fast storage (as described for DKRZ above).

Taking these in order:

(1) The ESIWACE problem is clearly large, and could benefit from the proposed developments.

(2) The existing large-scale workflows in WP1 are not production simulations in that they are “special capability simulations” and as such they involve only a few steps, and have little automated pre- and post-processing that would benefit from using a scheduler to stage multiple steps using the ESDM.

(3) Suitable systems. We had planned to deploy this system on at least on the DKRZ Mistral system and the UKRI ARCHER2 system, as well as any other suitable system available to the consortium. Unfortunately at this time, ARCHER2 is only just becoming available (over a year late) and the burst buffer system is not yet available, the DKRZ Lustre1 storage is fully utilised and not available, and no other system currently available to the consortium has more than one work storage system.

Under the circumstances there would be no benefit from using the developments we envisaged on these systems at this time for these particular workflows so we cannot actually test or evaluate anything we might build.

The remaining work should have involved modifying CYLC and providing glue code to integrate ESDM and control mechanisms for data placement. We still believe these ideas could be valuable in some system configurations and may proceed to make the necessary changes if we see some prospect for realistic gains for WP1 workflows (I.e during the evolution of this project). However, until we see that prospect, we believe the available engineering effort is better deployed on other tasks within this work package.

At the moment, it is sufficient that where ESIWACE partners wish to configure their workflow to exploit the ESDM, the storage is setup as usual within the model configuration. We will be testing it in such workflows, but we do not expect all the potential ESDM benefits unless there are sophisticated multi-level storage systems available, and there is no need for CYLC/ESDM integration without the addition of multi-step workflows. To that end, while we have not met the original milestone target of delivering the code necessary for integration, we have done all the necessary analysis, and believe that not formally delivering the code will not hinder the core project aims.

Kunkel, Julian M, and L. Pedro (2020): Potential of I/O Aware Workflows in Climate and Weather. *Supercomputing Frontiers and Innovations*, Series: Volume 7, Number 2, pp. 35-53, (Editors: Jack Dongarra, Vladimir Voevodin), Publishing Center of South Ural State University (454080, Lenin prospekt, 76, Chelyabinsk, Russia), ISSN: 2313-8734, <https://doi.org/10.14529/jsfi20020>.

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